

JUVENILE LABOR - DETERMINING LEGAL REGULATION IS A KEY FACTOR TO PREVENT HISTORY FROM REPEATING.

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Abstract. This article covers the statistics of children in the world, the history of minors' labor, analysis of their involvement in various harmful jobs, the prevalence of child labor in pre-industrial and industrial times, and the efforts made to prevent it .

It was concluded that the main reason for the cases of minors' use of labor at different levels in history was the insufficient development of laws in this regard, the absence of a control mechanism against child discrimination in labor, the rise of political instability, and the prevalence of famine and poverty .

Key words: population, poverty, industry, convention, statistics, child labor, need, famine, political instability.

Enterance

As soon as a person is born, natural needs arise with him. During the period of growth and maturity, the scope of needs expands further, and its composition is formed in different ways. will be able to receive.

Of course, the most important factor in this is human labor, and in a democratic legal society, unlimited needs can be provided only through the rational use of limited resources and human labor, and in this process, a person becomes socialized, realizes his dreams, and achieves a prosperous life.

Guaranteeing human rights and freedoms in labor relations, managing labor-related social life in society with laws and legal regulations, and making fair and reasonable decisions in this regard is an integral part of the development of every state.

At this point, the President of our country, Sh. Mirziyoev, expressed the following opinion about the importance of regulating labor relations:

"Ensuring reliable protection of human rights to work and decent living conditions, protection from unemployment, and reducing poverty is an important goal of constitutional reforms" [1].

According to Professor M.A. Usmanova, "ensuring human rights in the conditions of market relations, guaranteeing a decent living with labor and one's own labor, and social protection of the population are among the main aspects of the legislative activity of the Republic of Uzbekistan"[2].

In fact, a person matures through his work, acquires his place in society, enters into relations with members of society, and thereby becomes a participant in the labor market.

This, in turn, is to constantly improve the labor laws adopted in the country to provide employment to able-bodied persons, to allow every working person to live a comfortable life, to freely choose a profession, to work in decent working conditions, and to prevent any discrimination. In this regard, based on today's demand, consistent reforms are required.

In almost all countries, the professions that can be worked in are divided into types, and the people who can work in these professions are also classified according to their age; that is, the professions that adults and minors can work in depend on their age, ability, physical and mental readiness, and some other factors. It is established that he has the right to work under working conditions.

In this regard, the rules and conditions of labor relations for minors, who make up a certain part of the population in terms of numbers and cannot be equal to others, are defined separately in order to protect them in every way.

However, due to economic crises, poverty, political instability, and other factors in some countries, children are being used for various purposes against their best interests.

According to the statistics of the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), the number of people under the age of eighteen was 1.86 billion in the 1980s, 2.06 billion in the 1990s, 2.20 billion in the 2000s, and 2.25 billion in the 2010s. 2.38 billion in 2020 and 2.39 billion in 2023 [3].

In the world's poorest countries, slightly more than one in five children is involved in child labor [4].

According to the International Labor Organization, about 160.0 million children are still engaged in labor today [5].

It is known from the above that although the work of minors has existed from history to the present day at various levels, unlike the work of adults in some aspects, since this concept is not defined separately, they are involved in almost any kind of work.

Some sources state that the term "child labor" should not be confused with the concepts of "youth employment" or "student labor." [6].

Some historians believe that child labor was an integral part of the pre-industrial economy. In pre-industrial societies, the concept of childhood in the modern sense was rare.

Children are often actively involved in activities such as raising children, hunting, and farming. In many societies, children under the age of ten were engaged in the same activities as adults because they looked like adults—that is, they were physically equal to them [7].

The Industrial Revolution first began in Great Britain in the mid-eighteenth century, and the early 19th century was a period of massive mechanization and innovation that spread throughout the world [8].

During these periods, working conditions for women and children remained difficult. Women usually helped children transport the coal they mined. This process was particularly common in the early 19th century, when they pulled a corf (basket or small wagon) full of coal along tracks up to 16 inches (1 inch = 2.54 cm) [9] high, often working 12-hour shifts [10].

Finally, as soon as the International Labor Organization was established as a specialized body of the United Nations in 1919, efforts were first made to reduce the labor of women and children at the international level.

Today, the International Labor Organization is in its 1973 Conventions. 138 on the Minimum Age. 182 on the Worst Forms of Child Labor of 1999 were adopted and are considered to be one of the main international instruments regulating child labor worldwide.

In conclusion, we can state that in history, almost all countries have used child labor to varying degrees, and the main reasons for this are insufficient laws, a lack of control against discrimination in labor, increasing political instability, and the prevalence of famine and poverty. Today, we can see that the ILO is implementing huge reforms on child labor, and as a result, many children are being effectively protected.

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